

Emergencies

Using video based tools to find out what to do in an emergency.

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Categories?

Help?

A platform for help and support videos?

Emergencies

Finding help using video based tools

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Categories?

Help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Emergencies

Using image based resources to find out what to do in an emergency.

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

A platform for help and support videos?

Help?

Emergencies

Finding help using image based tools

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Categories?

Help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Emergencies

Using text-to-speech software with a variety of texts to find help and information during an emergency.

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

More free features?

Help?

Simpler processes?

Emergencies

Using text-to-speech software with a variety of texts to find help and information during an emergency.

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

More free features?

Help?

Simpler processes?

Emergencies

Using text-to-speech software with a variety of texts to find out what to do in an emergency.

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

More free features?

Help?

Simpler processes?

Emergencies

Using text-to-speech software to prepare for emergencies.

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

More free features?

Help?

Simpler processes?

Emergencies

Using text-to-speech
software to fill
in forms online

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Integrated
microphone?

Help?

Simpler
processes?

Emergencies

Using text- to-speech to send messages

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Integrated
microphone?

Simpler
processes?

Help?

Emergencies

Setting up your
device to be
user friendly
based on your
needs

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Integrated
microphone?

Help?

Simpler
processes?

Emergencies

Finding help
and support
online from
people or
groups

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Help?

Simpler
processes?

Emergencies

Using video based tools to find out how to prepare for an emergency.

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

More free features?

Help?

Simpler processes?

Emergencies

Using image based tools to find out how to prepare for an emergency.

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Categories?

Help?

A platform for help and support videos?

Emergencies

Using note
taking, planning
and visual tools
to prepare for
an emergency

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Help?

Emergencies

Using different
apps to find help
in an
emergency.

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Help?

Emergencies

**Creating personal
memos reminding
yourself what to
do in an
emergency.**

Existing tools

**Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...**

What would help?

Simpler processes?

Help?

